

**EFFECTS OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE HEALTH, ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE AND COPING MECHANISMS OF SENIOR HIGH
SCHOOL STUDENTS AT SAINT JOSEPH COLLEGE,
MAASIN CITY, SOUTHERN LEYTE**

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Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Health, Academic Performance and Coping Mechanisms of Senior High School Students at Saint Joseph College, Maasin City, Southern Leyte

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Abstract

This study investigated the extent of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health, academic performance, and coping mechanisms of the Grade 11 and 12 students of Saint Joseph College, Maasin City, Southern Leyte. The survey questionnaire was given to randomly selected 300 students and the results were statistically treated with an equal number of female and male students. The descriptive-correlational method of research was utilized and the questionnaire was adopted and modified from the DASS-21, Symptoms of Stress, BMSLSS- PTPB, DSES, and Coping Mechanisms. The study's findings reveal that the spiritual health was significantly affected, the social health was affected, and both the physical and mental health were slightly affected. Academic performance was outstanding, yet, few got failing grades, and coping mechanisms were often practiced. Among the profiles, age and gender has a significant relationship with health. There is a significant relationship between health and academic performance. Only the gender profile has a significant relationship with coping. The coping mechanisms and academic performance has a significant relationship. There is a significant difference in coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their gender. A health intervention plan was developed based on the findings of the study.

Keywords: *COVID-19 pandemic, health, spiritual health, social health, physical health, mental health*

Introduction

The pandemic has caused a disruptive effect on the lifestyle of the people and generated imminent risk, and has shocked sectors of society throughout the world. The situation compelled government leaders to put measures to control the stem of the coronavirus. These included mandatory quarantines and lockdowns (Hiremath et al., 2020; Atalan, 2020), reduced social contact, social distancing, constant wearing of face masks in public areas, mobility restrictions (WHO, 2021; Adhikari et al., 2020), and school closures to stem the spread of the virus (Viner et al., 2020).

These mitigations have moderately lessened the cases of infection, but they triggered another concern in all fields of society. When universities and colleges enacted temporary school closures, 1.5 billion students from 130 countries were seriously affected (UNESCO, 2021). The interruptions included delayed graduation, withdrawal from classes, cancellation of extracurricular activities like sports competitions, practicums, job offers, reductions in remuneration for certain working scholars, and most students experiencing family members who had lost a job (Aucejo et al., 2020; Kreitz, 2020).

Most institutions struggled to reopen for in-person learning the next academic year and resorted to a new mode of instruction such as remote education. However, some empirical investigations reported that the new modality impacted senior high school because it was the peak of the high school experience and a transition to college life (Kreitz, 2020). The prohibition of face-to-face learning and the move to remote education has undoubtedly affected these students since they went through an unprecedented interruption in their lives, anxious about their graduation or qualification and college admission preparations.

In the Philippines, studies have stated that the significant implications of the COVID-19 pandemic have led to a significant psychological impact and students missing out on usual school activities. The pandemic brought an unusual combination of the public health crisis, social isolation, and economic crisis that would most likely exacerbate an existing health problem and generate additional concerns among children and adolescents (Terada, 2020).

Students in the regions and provinces also felt these various consequences, such that in Southern Leyte, the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic was the stigma, exclusion, and mental health, caused by isolation, which harmed the learners, leading to depression, anxiety, stress, self-harm, and suicide (Kahambing & Edillo, 2020). The researcher assumed that the SHS students of Saint Joseph College were no exception. The current scenario might aggravate an existing health problem, resulting in poor academic performance and inappropriate coping techniques.

The researcher hoped to bridge a knowledge gap since research about children and adolescents was quite limited (Lee, 2020). However, studies focusing on the effects of the pandemic on the health, such as the mental, physical, social well-being, and spiritual aspect among senior high school students, its impact on the academic performance, and the coping mechanisms implemented as they deal with the pandemic situation were lacking, and the present study aimed to fill the gap.

There were studies on the effects of COVID-19 among Senior High School students, but its pinnacle is more on the mental health or psychological impacts and suicidal ideation or those who have prior mental health issues and special needs (Hou et al., 2020; Giannopoulou, Efstathiou, Triantafyllou, Korkoliakou & Douzenis, 2020; Lee, 2020). There was a gap in the academic literature on studies examining physical, social, and primarily spiritual aspects.

The research aimed to identify the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health, academic performance, and coping mechanisms of the senior high school students because the most growing body of literature focuses on some health-related behavior, such as aggression and violence, nutrition, sleep, unhealthy eating, physical inactivity, and substance abuse. The increasing health concern posed by the coronavirus fills a knowledge gap.

Given the preceding considerations, mindful of the widespread and far-reaching effects of the pandemic, the researcher was interested in measuring its impact on the health of Senior high school students at Saint Joseph College, Maasin City, Southern Leyte.

In this study, the researcher aims to contribute to Psychology and Education by determining the impact of COVID-19 on the health of Senior high school students at Saint Joseph College, Maasin City, Southern Leyte their coping mechanisms and how the school can support their well-being by providing appropriate interventions.

Research Questions

This study identified the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Health, Academic Performance, and Coping Mechanisms of Senior High School Students of Saint Joseph College, Maasin City, Southern Leyte, in the school year 2020- 2021. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Senior High School students in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. grade level; and
 - 1.4. combined monthly family income?
2. To what extent does the COVID-19 pandemic affect the health of the students in terms of:
 - 2.1. mental health;
 - 2.2. physical health;
 - 2.3. social health; and
 - 2.4. spiritual health?
3. What is the academic performance of the students?
4. To what extent are the coping mechanisms used by the students?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of students and their health?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the health and academic performance of students?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the students and coping mechanisms?
8. Is there a significant relationship between coping mechanisms and academic performance?
9. Is there a significant difference in the coping mechanisms of the students when grouped according to their profile?
10. What intervention plan can be proposed based on the findings?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design was descriptive-correlational since it describes a phenomenon and the cause or effect of a situation under study and measures a relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling either of them. The method is appropriate since it intends to describe the profile of the respondents, the extent of the impact of the pandemic on their health, academic performance, and the extent of employment of the coping mechanisms. Also, it identified the correlations between the profile of the respondents and the health, health, and academic performance, the profile and the coping mechanisms, the coping mechanisms, and the academic performance, and the significant difference in coping mechanisms when grouped according to their profile.

In terms of approach, it used the quantitative approach, which focuses on obtaining numerical findings with the use of a survey questionnaire.

Respondents

The respondents in this study were the 300 randomly selected Grade 11 and Grade 12 students of Saint Joseph College, Maasin City, Southern Leyte. The random sampling technique gave all senior high school students an equal chance of being included in the sample. The total number of students for the school year 2020-2021 was 1,200, and using Slovin's formula it determined a 300 number of respondents that best represents the total population. The researcher opted to have a 50% from grade 11 and 50% from grade 12 and half of whom were male, and the other half were female to have an equal representation by gender.

Instruments

The questionnaire was adopted and modified from Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scales–21 Items (DASS-21), designed to measure the emotional states of depression, anxiety, and stress (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995); the Symptoms of Stress, a 12 item self-report assessment tool used to identify the experience of common physical symptoms of stress (NYSUT,2013); Brief Multidimensional

Students' Life Satisfaction Scale–Peabody Treatment Progress Battery (BMSLSS- PTPB), a 6-items test used to identify the satisfaction of the social well-being intended for adolescent (Athay, Douglas Kelley & Dew-Reeves, 2012); Daily Spiritual Experiences Scale (DSES), a 16-items self-report measurement of spiritual experiences that aims to measure ordinary and daily spiritual experiences (Underwood, 2006) and coping mechanism among youth, a 10 item survey regarding the coping mechanisms they have applied during the pandemic (Dangi et al., 2020). There were modifications to the self-report scales to fit the needs of this study.

The tool has three parts: the first part contains the demographic profile of the respondents, and the second part, the health in terms of mental, physical, social, and spiritual which the respondents determined how each statement applies to them. The last part was about the extent of coping mechanisms used by them.

The study applied the Cronbach Alpha to the findings of 100 SHS students to examine the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire, yielding a coefficient value of 0.86 that shows that the questions in the survey were reliable.

Procedure

The researcher secured all the requirements needed to conduct the study, such as the clearance from the Ethical Committee of the university and the approval of the Dean of the Graduate school and dissertation adviser.

The Executive Vice-President of Saint Joseph College and the Principal of the Senior High School Department granted the researcher permission to float the questionnaire and pretested and validated the research instrument to 100 SHS students. After that, the researcher sent the informed consent and assent to the randomly selected students before the research instrument.

The researcher requested the academic performance of the respondents from their corresponding advisers. The gathering, tabulating, analysis, and interpretation of the data followed.

Data Analysis

The researcher encoded, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the data collected. The following statistical tools processed the data through Statistical Package for Social Sciences v.24 and specifically:

The Simple Percentage was used in identifying the profile of the respondents, and academic performance. The Average Weighted Mean was used to determine the extent of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health, and coping mechanisms while the Coefficient of Contingency was used for the correlations of variables. On the other hand, ANOVA to assess if there is a in the significant differences in the coping mechanisms of the students when grouped according to their profile.

Ethical Considerations

To address various concerns in preserving the privacy and security of the respondents, the researcher followed integrity and supported the Data Privacy Law and kept their identities and information discreet.

The researcher presented and discussed the informed consent and assent to the respondents before the conduct of the study to give them the freedom to decline their participation (see Appendix B & C). To assure them of their privacy, the researcher followed these steps: (1) distinguishing and coding of data; (2) no particular identifying information or mark in the survey questionnaire or the computer; (3) a secure storage for the data throughout the study; (4) destroying of information after use

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, analysis, discussion, interpretation, and implications of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health, academic performance, and coping mechanisms of senior high school students of Saint Joseph College, Maasin City, Southern Leyte.

Profile of the Respondents

The profile included the age, gender, grade level, and combined monthly family income of 300 randomly selected SHS students of Saint Joseph College. Tables 2 to 5 present the findings.

Age profile. Table 2 below projects the frequency and percentage of the respondents' age in years.

Table 1. *Age Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
19 years old and above	35	11.37
18 years old	113	37.67
17 years old	118	39.33
16 years old and below	34	11.33
Total	300	100

Table 1 reveals the ages of the 300 respondents which ranged from 16 years old and below to 19 years old and above. About 11.33%

of the respondents were 16 years old and below, 39.33% were 17 years old, 37.67% were 18 years old, and 11.37% were 19 years old and above. The result shows a significantly high proportion of the population for ages 17-18 years, and a minimal but almost equal number of 16 years old and below and 18 years old and above. The findings pinpointed that a substantial number of respondents between the ages of 17-18 years fell within the age range for SHS learners in the Philippine Educational System. The minimal percentage of respondents aged 16 years old and below were the learners who started school early, and the few frequencies for those aged 19 years old and above showed that they either attended school late, dropped or stopped in their studies for some time, or repeated a grade level.

Granada (2021) stated that when the Philippine government implemented the K to 12 programs, children were required to attend kindergarten at age five (5) to SHS. The Grade 11 students were commonly at 16-17 years of age while Grade 12 students were 17-18 years old. However, not all students had a continuous study since others had dropped, stopped, or repeated a grade level. Romero (2021) reported that the difficult circumstances associated with the COVID-19 pandemic forced students to stop and drop school.

Gender profile. In this study, gender was classified into two categories, male and female. Table 2 illustrates the proportion of male and female respondents.

Table 2 below displays a total of 300 respondents, wherein 150 are male, and 150 are female. The result shows a significant equal percentage of populations from each gender. The finding demonstrated an equal perspective of the topic understudy from both genders.

Table 2. Gender Profile of the Respondents

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	150	50
Female	150	50
Total	300	100

The researcher purposively planned for a balanced representation of male and female respondents on the apparent effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on their health, academic performance, and the extent of coping mechanisms employed since it was considered that males and females differed in physical, mental, social, and spiritual development and composition. It could also be deduced that the pandemic had an impact on everyone.

The result implies that the balanced representation of the perspectives of both genders assured valid and reliable findings since the data were well representative. This notion is similar to the idea of Patino and Ferreira (2018), who stated that the number of populations influenced external validity.

Grade level profile. In the Philippine educational system, the Senior High School students go through two grade levels, namely, Grade 11 and Grade 12. The data obtained are reflected in the table below.

Table 3. Grade Level Profile of the Respondents

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
Grade 11	150	50
Grade 12	150	50
Total	300	100

Table 3 shows a total of 300 Grade 11 and Grade 12 respondents. About 50 % of students are in Grade 11, and the other 150 are in Grade 12. According to the data, the percentage of respondents from each grade was substantially the same. The researcher purposefully selected an equal number of respondents from each grade level to ensure a balanced representation of Grade 11 and Grade 12 respondents on the apparent effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly in their health, academic performance, and the extent of coping mechanisms employed. It was taken into account since Grades 11 and 12 present different challenges, expected learning competencies, and levels of cognition.

As underlined by Patino and Ferreira (2018), the population size impacted the external validity of the study. Furthermore, each grade level had a different set of competencies to master and learn, and a chosen career track defined the content of the subjects that students took within every grade level (Brilantes, Orbeta, Francisco- Abrigo, Capones & Jovellanos, 2019).

Combined Monthly Family Income. The combined monthly family income refers to the monetary resources acquired by the family each month, which was classified using the Philippine Statistics Authority's 2018 Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES). The data obtained are presented in the table below.

Table 4 summarizes the findings based on the Combined Monthly Family Income of the respondents. The findings reveal that 55.33 % of the 300 SHS respondents belonged to the poor income cluster, 11.67% were from middle- middle-income households, and 9% were from lower-middle-income households. A significantly high percentage of respondents fell into the poor income cluster, defined as earning less than the official poverty line. The middle-middle-income class (11.67%) outnumbered the lower-middle-income class (9%).

Table 4. Combined Monthly Family Income

Combined Monthly Family Income	Income Cluster	Definition	Frequency	Percentage
Php 41,000 and above	Middle-middle income class	Between four and seven times the poverty line	35	11.67
Php 26,000 to 40,000	Lower middle - income class	Between two and four times the poverty line	27	9
Php 10,000 to 25,000	Low-income class (but not poor)	Between the poverty line and twice the poverty line	72	24
Below Php10,000	Poor	Less than the official poverty threshold	166	55.33
Total			300	100

The ongoing existence of the COVID-19 pandemic and the shift from in-person to remote learning has given rise to new worries, such as the procurement of computers, cellular phones, gadgets, internet access, and loads to support their educational venture.

Moreover, there were few respondents whose monthly family income ranged from PHP 41,000 and above. Such household experienced a certain degree of freedom and security, flexibility in their spending, and availability of resources.

The pandemic aggravated the situation; economic drops were noticeable, as some people lost their jobs, temporary closure of businesses, and restrictions on travel. These measures helped reduce the number of people affected, but it led to a loss of opportunity to earn their daily income.

Data show that the majority of respondents were having financial difficulties and the pandemic likely worsened it because of the worldwide economic recession.

Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Health

The study investigated the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health of senior high school students at Saint Joseph College in Maasin City, Southern Leyte, through a survey questionnaire. The four health indicators were mental, physical, social, and spiritual. The gathered data were analyzed and interpreted using the average weighted mean. Tables 5 to 9 present the results.

Mental Health. Ten self-report statements on tendencies and normal reactions were used in the assessment of the extent of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on their mental health. The gathered information is provided in the following tables.

Table 5. Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Mental Health

	Statements	AWM	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Description	Rank
1.	I tended to overreact to situations.	1.50	0.774	Applied to me to a considerable degree	Affected	6
2.	I found it difficult to relax.	1.63	0.880	Applied to me to a considerable degree	Affected	1
3.	I was intolerant of anything that kept me from getting on with what I was doing.	1.52	0.756	Applied to me to a considerable degree	Affected	4
4.	I felt that I was using a lot of nervous energy.	1.55	0.900	Applied to me to a considerable degree	Affected	3
5.	I felt scared without any good reason.	1.47	0.996	Applied to me sometimes	Slightly Affected	7
6.	I felt that I was close to panicking.	1.25	0.979	Applied to me sometimes	Slightly Affected	10
7.	I was worried about situations in which I might panic and make a fool of myself.	1.52	0.986	Applied to me to a considerable degree	Affected	5
8.	I was unable to become enthusiastic about anything.	1.41	0.867	Applied to me sometimes	Slightly Affected	8
9.	I found it difficult to work up the initiative to do things.	1.61	0.808	Applied to me to a considerable degree	Affected	2
10.	I felt that I wasn't worth much as a person.	1.40	1.034	Applied to me sometimes	Slightly Affected	9
	Overall Mean	1.49	0.595	Applied to me sometimes	Slightly Affected	

Legend: 2.25 - 3.00 Applied to me most of the time; Very Much Affected; 1.50 - 2.24 Applied to me to a considerable degree; Affected; 0.75 - 1.49 Applied to me sometimes; Slightly Affected; 0 - 0.74 Did not apply to me at all; Not Affected

Table 5 presents the result on the degree of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic to their mental health. With an average weighted mean score of 1.63, the statement, "I found it difficult to relax," takes first place in the rankings. On the other hand, with an average weighted mean score of 1.25, the statement, "I felt that I was close to panic," is in rank 10. The overall mean score garners a 1.49 average weighted mean score with a standard deviation of 0.595.

A relatively high average weighted mean score on the statement, "I found it difficult to relax," indicated that the respondents experienced it to a considerable degree. Similarly, the statement, "I felt I was close to panic," suggested a moderate effect, which respondents specified that this happened to them occasionally.

The substantial overall mean score of 1.49 signified that the COVID-19 pandemic had slightly affected their mental health, and the low

standard deviation score of 0.595 highlighted that most of the answers in the data set were the same. The result revealed that it was difficult for the respondents to relax during the COVID-19 pandemic. This specific behavior was manifested when a person felt the need to move constantly, could not rest their mind and focus or a mix of the two.

The figures in the table suggest that the inability to relax as a reaction is a significant manifestation of anxiety in a person. It was most often felt when individuals were confronted with various demands and concerns that caused them to feel fearful and uneasy.

For instance, the current COVID-19 pandemic made dramatic changes in the lives of the respondents and instilled fear of infections, as well as uncertainties about the matters vital to them, which caused anxiety, particularly demonstrated in the inability to relax.

Based on a thorough examination of the data, it is implied that the COVID-19 pandemic had a modest impact on the mental health of the learner, caused them to feel nervous and close to panic. However, it could be lessened by relaxing indoor activities such as deep breathing, yoga, meditation, and exercise.

Adolescents, according to Morin (2020), were more stressed than adults. Their concerns were focused on unfulfilled needs related to school, friends, relationships, their future, and money. According to Hagerty and Williams (2020), denying these particular desires would be detrimental to one's mental health.

Likewise, Terada (2020) stressed that adolescents were more vulnerable to any social and psychological changes during this time because of the unique combination of the public health crisis and economic recession. Mainly, this economic fallout triggered other profound worry and stress that was detrimental to mental health (Robinson & Smith, 2020).

Moreover, the finding conformed to the results of numerous studies, which specified that with the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, the adverse effect was more on mental health (Ornell et al., 2020; Terada, 2020; Hou et al., 2020; Giannopoulou et al., 2020; Lee, 2020). Additionally, they have foreseen that the number of affected individuals in their mental health was more significant than those affected by the virus (Ornell et al., 2020). As pointed out by Zhou et al. (2020), the pandemic is a stressful situation that triggers mental health-related issues.

Similarly, AlAzzam Abuhammad, Tawalbeh and Dalky (2021) declared that the current situation had amplified these mental health issues among adolescents. However, Gruebner (2017) declared that there were fewer reports on mental health cases in rural areas than the urban areas. In rural areas, being in touch with nature, trees, and fresh air was still abundant. Also, Grima, Corcoran, Hill-James, Langton, Sommer, and Fisher, (2020) stressed that access to these areas was beneficial to mental health.

Over time, present mental health concerns might become severe and persistent, worsening a mental health condition. This necessitated the strict implementation of mental health policies by the government and educational institutions to reduce the risk of increased mental health cases.

Physical Health. The table below identifies the ten self-reported physical symptoms ranked based on the average weighted mean result. The table also includes verbal interpretations and descriptions.

Table 6. *Effects of COVID-19 pandemic on the Physical Health*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>AWM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Headaches	1.43	0.924	Once a week	Affected	3.5
2.	Tense muscle, sore neck, and back	1.43	0.988	Once a week	Affected	3.5
3.	Fatigue	1.04	1.016	Once a month	Slightly Affected	6
4.	Difficulty falling asleep	1.79	1.107	Once week	Affected	2
5.	Insomnia	1.26	1.232	Once a month	Slightly Affected	5
6.	Eating too much or too little.	1.87	0.970	Once a week	Affected	1
7.	Diarrhea, cramps, gas, constipation	0.75	0.723	Once a month	Slightly Affected	9
8.	Restlessness, itching, tics.	0.89	0.887	Once a month	Slightly Affected	8
9.	Chest pain and rapid heartbeat	0.95	0.965	Once a month	Slightly Affected	7
10.	Frequent colds and infections.	0.60	0.713	Never	Not Affected	10
	Overall AWM	1.20	0.629	Once a month	Slightly Affected	

Legend: 2.25 - 3.00 Everyday; Very Much Affected; 1.50 - 2.24 Once a week; Affected; 0.75 - 1.49 Once a month; Slightly Affected; 0 - 0.74 Never; Not Affected

Table 6 indicates the scope of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on physical health. The statement, "Eating too much or too little," receives an average weighted mean score of 1.87 and a standard deviation of 0.970. Also, the statements, "Headaches" and "Tense muscles, sore neck, and back," both receive the same 1.43 average weighted mean score, putting them in the same 3.5 ranking while the statement, "Frequent colds and infections," receives a weighted mean score of 0.60. The total result discloses an overall mean of 1.20.

Accordingly, among the bodily symptoms, "eating too much or too little," has a significant average weighted mean score, wherein the data described that the changes in their eating consumption were profoundly experienced once a week. Furthermore, the figures in the table reveal that headaches and tense muscle, sore neck and back have a similar degree of influence and that these symptoms were severely experienced by the pupils once a week. Furthermore, the statement, "Frequent colds and infections," received the lowest

average weighted mean, which indicates that they did not experience it.

This finding shows that the respondents' appetite fluctuated as a result of a variety of COVID-19 pandemic-related conditions that triggered people to consume less or more than their bodies required.

Among the compelling reasons considered by the researcher were changes in primary food access and availability, as well as the experience of food insecurity during the strict enforcement of COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns and quarantines. Families were advised to remain at home and stock up on food until pandemic quarantines and lockdowns were lifted.

In addition, this measure made a drastic change in their lifestyle and had altered their accustomed routines and daily activities. Adjustment to any change in the daily routine and structure also highlighted the change in their appetite.

Another significant finding of the study was the occurrence of headaches and tense muscle soreness in the neck and back once a week. It is difficult enough to deal with neck pain alone, let alone when it is accompanied by back pain and tense muscles that limit head mobility.

As a result, when a headache was present, increased pain might exacerbate the situation. These similar results suggested that it could have started as a sore neck and then spread to the head or that it could have started in the head and spread to the neck. This pain could also be attributed to the other, or these symptoms might occur concurrently.

The researcher considered some factors that contributed to these pains. First, the change in their eating consumption was parallel to not eating a balanced diet, skipping, and not eating nutritious food. All these could contribute to headaches.

The second factor was the deprivation of sleep which was verified in the table wherein the respondents indicated that they had "Difficulty falling asleep," with an average weighted mean score of 1.79. Third, tension headaches were caused by tensions and stress. Experts in the medical field often recommend that adolescents find regular time to relax to avoid tensions and stress.

Lastly, when the students were forced to stay at home, this lessened their physical and other activities such as daily living, going to school, leisure, and social gatherings. Moreover, this decrease in physical activities could have triggered headaches and other pains due to poor blood circulation.

Conversely, the respondents had never experienced frequent colds and infections. These symptoms were known to be among the manifestation of being infected by the coronavirus, and fortunately, the respondents were spared from it. Despite these compelling reasons, the overall result shows that the COVID-19 pandemic had a minor impact on their physical health. The following factors were thought to mediate the outcome.

Moreover, studies pointed out that the pandemic brought disruptions (Douglas et al., 2020) and an abrupt change in the lifestyle (Kang-Hyun, Kim, Yang, Lim & Park, 2021), which led to a lesser physical and other meaningful activities or an increase in sedentary behavior time (Zheng et al., 2020; Moore et al., 2020). These unhealthy practices result in headaches, body pains, or poor sleep (Ammar et al., 2020; Xiang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020).

According to the American Migraine Foundation (2016) and affirmed by Ng and Hanna (2021), these pains were commonly reported by adolescents. It was advised that one must schedule a relaxation period, reduce stress, balanced dietary intake, and eat regular meals, maintain a regular time to sleep and exercise the body to attain a healthy well-being.

Social Health. The table below displays the ten social relation dimensions ranks based on the average weighted mean result. The higher the average weighted mean score indicates an unsatisfactory experience from these dimensions.

Table 7. Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Social Health

Social Relation Dimensions	AWM	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Description	Rank
1. Your neighbors.	2.44	0.822	Did not experience a satisfying interaction	Very Much Affected	2
2. Your school experience.	2.60	0.722	Did not experience a satisfying interaction	Very Much Affected	1
3. Your teachers.	2.37	0.792	Did not experience a satisfying interaction	Very Much Affected	3
4. Your life overall.	2.25	0.885	Did not experience a satisfying interaction	Very Much Affected	5
5. Your parents.	1.75	0.875	Rarely experienced a satisfying interaction	Affected	10
6. Your friends.	1.99	0.824	Rarely experienced a satisfying interaction	Affected	8
7. Yourself.	2.34	0.871	Did not experience a satisfying interaction	Very Much Affected	4
8. Your family life.	1.94	0.971	Rarely experienced a satisfying interaction	Affected	9
9. Your place where you live.	2.17	0.981	Rarely experienced a satisfying interaction	Affected	7
10. Fun and bonding with friends.	2.22	0.888	Rarely experienced a satisfying interaction	Affected	6
Overall Mean	2.21	0.601	Rarely experienced a satisfying interaction	Affected	

Legend: 2.25 - 3.00 Did not experience a satisfying interaction; Very Much Affected; 1.50 - 2.24 Rarely experienced a satisfying interaction; Affected; 0.75 - 1.49 Sometimes experienced a satisfying interaction; Slightly Affected; 0 - 0.74 Always experienced a satisfying interaction; Not Affected

Table 7 reveals the strength of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the social health of the students. The table shows that the statements, "your school experience" ranks first among the ten social relationships, with an average weighted mean score of 2.60, and "Parents" ranks 10th with an average weighted mean score of 1.75. The overall mean is 2.21, with a standard deviation of 0.601. The

statement, "Your school experience," has a high average weighted mean result, which indicated that their school experience did not provide them with a pleasant encounter during the COVID-19 epidemic. In addition, "Your Parents" has shown a moderate result. Even though it got the lowest average weighted mean score, its magnitude indicated an affected social interaction. Furthermore, the social health result was relatively high, which revealed that most of respondents stated that they only had a few satisfying relationships. The low standard deviation highlighted that most of their responses were grouped around the mean score.

The findings suggest that the social relationship of the students was disrupted during this period of health crises in one way or the other. This led them to describe that they did not experience a satisfying relationship.

The loss of social interactions, daily school routine, and some school anticipated activities, such as the SJC Educative Family Days, Intramurals, socials, sports feast, cultural activities, and the like, that SJC had offered to the learners prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, were among the compelling reasons.

Moreover, these activities helped students engage with their teachers, made new friends, and developed their social skills. The COVID-19 pandemic, however, hampered these experiences. Although these social contacts have been moved to virtual platforms, as social beings, they do not replace the fulfilling interactions of in-person discourse.

This finding is similar to numerous undertakings that strongly highlight the impact of the pandemic on the social aspect. Notably, Spinelli, Lionetti, Setti, Fasolo (2020), WHO (2020), Morelli, Cattelino, Baiocco, Trumello, Babore, Candelori and Chirumbolo (2020) concluded that the pandemic had a negative consequence and was a crucial factor that undermined the social well-being of adolescents.

Hence, Douglas et al. (2020) and Kreitz (2020) pointed out that in this time of the pandemic, the mobility restrictions and the disruption of education had hindered the social interactions, the academic endeavors, and the loss of structure and daily routine, wherein these social scaffolds provided a sense of certainty and had conditioned and trained the brain to learn and develop. Lee (2020) stated that this disruption of education had impacted their social health since it impeded social interactions (Douglas et al., 2020).

Also, studies have indicated that their developmental need contributes to the extent of the effect of the pandemic since they are in a stage in life wherein the building of relationship are centered outside the home. This means that the parent- teen relationship shifts during this stage. The adherence to mobility restrictions has hampered these needs and confirmed the study of Hagerty and William (2020) which indicated that if these needs were not satisfied, they generated a detrimental effect on health.

Spiritual Health. The listed statements were typical of daily spiritual encounters of a person's life. These spiritual experiences were ranked based on the average weighted mean. The table below shows the result.

Table 8 shows the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on spiritual health. It reveals that "I feel thankful" ranks first among the ten statements with an average weighted mean score of 2.68. Similarly, the statement, "I forgive others even when they do things that are wrong," received an average weighted mean of 2.08. This statement ranks tenth. The average spiritual health score is 2.47, with a standard deviation of 0.548.

The statement, "I feel thankful," received a significantly higher average weighted mean score than the other statements. This demonstrated that respondents found it difficult to practice gratitude in their daily lives during the COVID-19 pandemic. Another notable result was the statement, "I accept others even when they do things that are wrong," which was at the bottom of the rankings but still has a significant impact. Most importantly, there was a profound overall effect on spiritual health.

Remarkably, the result indicates that the respondents were having difficulty feeling thankful given their painful experience and struggles to accept others even when they did things that were wrong, which also proposed that their tolerance in this time of pandemic was being challenged. Tolerance was established on looking beyond the considered wrong that divides people and virtue of resolving external conflict. However, the result illustrates that the respondents felt intolerant towards others.

Table 8. *Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Spiritual Health*

	<i>Statement</i>	<i>AWM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	I experience God's connection in my life.	2.47	0.733	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	5
2.	During worship or at other times, I feel joy, which lifts me out of my daily concerns.	2.34	0.739	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	9
3.	I find comfort in my religion or spirituality.	2.46	0.714	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	7
4.	I ask for God's help in the midst of daily activity.	2.58	0.677	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	3
5.	I feel God's love for me through others.	2.42	0.744	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	8
6.	I am spiritually touched by the beauty of creation.	2.47	0.724	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	6
7.	I feel guided by God amid daily activities.	2.56	0.699	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	4
8.	I feel thankful.	2.68	0.631	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	1
9.	I accept others even when they do things that I think are wrong.	2.08	0.776	Rarely experienced it	Affected	10
10.	I desire to be closer to God in union with Him.	2.66	0.622	Did not experience it	Very Much Affected	2
	Overall mean	2.47	0.548		Very Much Affected	

Legend: 2.25 - 3.00 Did not experience it; Very Much Affected; 1.50 - 2.24 Rarely experienced it; Affected; 0.75 - 1.49 Experienced it once in a while; Slightly Affected; 0 - 0.74 Experienced it everyday; Not Affected

Moreover, the pandemic has overturned the lifestyle of the people overnight, and Ghaderi et al. (2018) stated that spiritual health was a connection with self, others, nature, and God, which was manifested in the appropriate daily lifestyle. However, the COVID-19 pandemic, new normal lifestyle had altered and deprived this sense of connection with others (Hagerty & Williams, 2020), and deficiency across each need triggered a detrimental effect on the spiritual health.

Furthermore, Ghaderi et al. (2018) and Hoosen et al. (2020) have emphasized that spiritual health was nurtured through spiritual practices. These practices were recognized to be powerful tools in dealing with life-changing and traumatic events such as the pandemic. However, these preventive measures prohibit people from gathering for religious functions and celebrating spiritual practices, which was an essential pillar for social and mutual support (WHO, 2021; Adhikari et al., 2020).

The study conducted on Italian respondents in the same context indicated that spirituality and religious practices served as a protective factor that supported the individual going through the difficulties encountered during the pandemic (Coppola, Rania, Parisi & Lagomarsino, 2021). The spirituality and religiosity were strengthened and at the same time mediated the reaction during any difficulties. The COVID-19 pandemic compounded the difficulties. These changes in the routines, according to Humphreys, Myint and Zeanah (2020), have triggered the students to feel upset, confused, and difficult to handle. These difficulties in everyday living were considered by many Filipino Catholic Youths as a trial of faith that causes moral and physical pain, and the COVID-19 pandemic had worsened the situation. These difficulties in life have tested the strength of their faith.

Furthermore, Del Castillo and Alino (2020) explained that one must accept the universal truth that difficulties and problems are inevitable. With this notion in heart, this allows the person to transcend the challenges of daily living as oneness with the sufferings of Christ.

On the contrary, studies on the development of adolescents, show that the maturation of cognitive processes that allow them to understand more complex and abstract concepts better were still developing, coupled with rapid emotional changes (Children's Health, 2016). Hence, they should be better equipped with religious practices for them to make meaning in all situations that come in their lives and deepen their faith. Also, adolescents might readily handle the cognitive complexity and practice these spiritual experiences daily if they were guided.

In general, it could be deduced that the life-changing events brought by the COVID-19 could had been an avenue to deepen the relationship with God and enrich one's spiritual health.

Over-all Health. Mental, physical, social, and spiritual health were the indicators included in the study. The table below discloses the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on overall health.

Table 9. *Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Health*

<i>Health Indicators</i>	<i>AWM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Mental Health	1.49	0.595	Slightly Affected
Physical Health	1.20	0.629	Slightly Affected
Social Health	2.21	0.601	Affected
Spiritual Health	2.47	0.548	Very Much Affected
Overall Mean	1.85	0.593	Affected

Legend: 2.25 - 3.00 Very Much Affected; 1.50 - 2.24 Affected; 0.75 - 1.49 Slightly Affected; 0 - 0.74 Not Affected

Table 9 shows the scope of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on health. Mental and physical health are classified as Slightly Affected, with average weighted mean scores of 1.49 and 1.20, respectively. Spiritual health has an average weighted mean score of 2.47, which is severely affected. The total mean score for health is 1.87, with a standard deviation of 0.593.

The findings demonstrate a parallel slightly affected description of the extent of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental and the physical health of the students. Also, the findings suggest that they were the least affected among the four health indicators. The spiritual health result reveals that, of the four health indicators, this one was the most affected. With that, the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on overall health.

The result reveals that among the four health indicators, physical health gets the lowest average weighted mean score, but if based on the given description on the level of effect, it has the same result with mental health. This least affected physical health was attributed mainly to their developmental stage. Adolescents were considered not part of the vulnerable group to be highly infected by the coronavirus due to their strong immunity.

Furthermore, the result highlights a profoundly affected spiritual health among the four health indicators. Spiritual health is a distinct and harmonious relationship with self, others, and God, manifested in daily living. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has disturbed the normal lifestyle, and the new normal has enforced a lessened connection with others, posing new challenges that adolescents find very overwhelming, thus, affected their spiritual health.

However, when all the health indicators were inclusively taken together, it signifies that the COVID-19 pandemic had affected the respondent's health. It is also evident that the 0.593 standard deviation result of all four health indicators suggest that most of the answers of the respondents were closer to the mean score. This signifies that the majority of them have declared that the COVID-19

pandemic has affected their health. The figures on the table imply that the pandemic considerably affected the health of the respondents and that they had almost similar views, as indicated in the small value of the standard deviation.

Academic Performance of the Students

The Academic performance referred to in this study is the general average grade the students acquired at the end of the first semester in the academic year 2020-2021. It pertains to the consolidated rating from all the subjects they had undertaken. Table 11 presents the gathered data.

Table 10. *Academic Performance of the Students*

<i>Numerical Value</i>	<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
90% and above	Outstanding	161	53.67
80 % -89%	Satisfactory	80	26.67
75 % -79%	Fairly Satisfactory	44	14.67
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	15	5.00
	Total	300	100

The table reveals that 53.67% of the total 300 research population indicates an outstanding grade, with a numerical value of 90% and above, while 15 respondents show a failing grade of below 75.

The data notably exhibit a high percentage of respondents with a grade of 90% and above which indicated that majority of the learners were performing well academically. There is a significant minimal number of the respondents who achieved a grade below 75, which suggested that they did not meet the passing grade.

In the K to 12 Basic Education Program, a standard and competency-based grading system is used. All grades are based on the weighted raw score of the learners' summative assessments. The minimum grade needed to pass a specific learning area is 60, which is transmuted to 75 in the report card.

Given the abovementioned grading system in the Philippine Educational system, it can be implied that most respondents have completed all required written works, such as assignments and quizzes, engaged in online classes, and completed all required performance tasks on time. Most importantly, the learners passed the Quarterly tests with a high passing rate. All these factors were completed by the students.

However, the minimal number of the respondents who achieved a grade below 75 failed to acquire the passing grade needed. This indicates that these 15 respondents were not able to submit the required written work such as the assignments and quizzes, failed to comply with the required performance tasks, and failed in the quarterly exams. Mainly, they were not able to comply with the given remedial activities.

These students might have varied reasons for their inability to submit the requirements, such as the unavailability of the needed gadgets and internet connectivity, and the stand that some students might have difficulty in understanding the lesson much more left to do it on their own. Above all, the financial issues that had worsened during this time could influence the lack of endeavor to pursue their academic journey.

Kuhfeld, Soland, Tarasawa, Johnson, Ruzek and Liu (2020) stated that lower achievement and academic loss were the typical findings of numerous research since parents, educators, and even students had stated that learning was even more complicated when it was done out of school due to stay-at-home advisory.

In the K to 12 Basic Educational Program, learners from Grades 1 to 12 are graded on Written Work, Performance Tasks, and Quarterly Assessment every quarter. These three are given specific percentage weights that vary according to the nature of the learning area (Llego, n.d.). However, Almerino et al. (2020) emphasized that with the new educational challenges brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, to minimize the effect of the crisis, teachers and educational front runners must construct simplified assessments which should not be a replica of the in-person teaching since paper and pen type of assessment was not suitable with the new modality, for students to have a better and passing academic performance.

Coping Mechanisms

The coping mechanisms presented in this study are the activities that adolescents were inclined to do during the COVID-19 pandemic. These have been ranked based on the highest average weighted mean score to the lowest result. The result is presented in Table 11.

Table 12 shows the result of the coping mechanisms practiced by the students during the pandemic. Among the ten coping mechanisms "using mobile and social media at a maximum time of the day" ranks first with a significant high average weighted mean score of 2.28. The coping, "Doing yoga and meditation to relieve stress," garners an average weighted mean score of 0.89. The overall coping mechanisms garner a general mean score of 1.60, and 0.337 standard deviation result.

The table shows a significantly high result for mobile and social media use most of the time. This result indicates that this coping was done on a daily basis. There is also a noteworthy low result for coping with yoga and meditation to relieve stress which revealed that

this coping was not of their particular interest. This coping was only performed once a month. Furthermore, the modest overall result suggests that respondents frequently used coping methods in dealing with the unexpected obstacles posed by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Moreover, the finding disclosed that the students were inclined to cope through the use of social media and mobile phones at the maximum time of the day. The greatest time consumption entailed being on their phones from early in the morning until late in the evening. Even before the pandemic, people of all ages used social media and were users of mobile games as a coping technique. This platform assisted them to socially connect and interact, build relationships, and for some individuals, this was the avenue through which they could create their social persona while others engaged in putting the negative emotions on a normal ground to cope with feelings of loneliness and boredom and try to make them feel better.

However, when students were compelled to stay at home during the lockdown and the learning mode was changed to online, the respondents began to make extensive use of their mobile phones and social media. As they continue their studies, the platform has now become a channel for them to socially engage and converse with their teachers. These were just a handful of the compelling reasons that led to the outcome.

In addition, yoga and meditation were also identified as coping strategies that would be good to their health, particularly during this time of health crisis. Students, on the other hand, stated that they practiced yoga occasionally or once a month. This coping method was utilized to reduce tension, but because it was not yet ingrained in Filipino society, students employed it on occasion, because it takes time and practice to fully get in touch with the inner self.

Overall, the findings revealed that students used coping methods once each week on average. The mode of coping employed by these students was very striking. The use of social media and mobile phones were ways and means for respondents to cope, connect, and obtain information; yet, the length of time they adhered to this platform was detrimental to their health and quality of life.

With this observation, the result indicates that students often use coping techniques to adjust to the changes and obstacles brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic, but their mode of coping and length could lead to another significant health problem.

Table 11. *Extent of Coping Mechanisms used by Students*

<i>Coping Mechanisms</i>	<i>AWM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Using mobile and social media maximum time of my day.	2.28	.794	Everyday	Always	1
Engaging myself in household activities like cooking, cleaning, and gardening, etc.	2.16	.798	Once a week	Often	2
Getting more quality time with my family.	2.09	.893	Once a week	Often	3
Using my time on my hobbies.	1.96	.831	Once a week	Often	4
Find opportunities to learn some productive things.	1.94	.767	Once a week	Often	5
Spending my time sleeping.	1.72	.840	Once a week	Often	6
More time to connect with friends through phone calls/video.	1.64	.924	Once a week	Often	7
Time for exercise and work out at home.	1.45	.896	Once a month	Sometimes	8
More time in watching TV than usual.	1.17	.923	Once a month	Sometimes	9
Doing yoga and meditation to relieve stress.	0.89	.929	Once a month	Sometimes	10
Overall Mean	1.60	.337	Once a week	Often	

Legend: 2.25 - 3.00 Everyday; Always; 1.50 - 2.24 Once a week; Often; 0.75 - 1.49 Once a month; Sometimes; 0 - 0.74 Did not practice; Never

With this, the result implies that the plurality of students at SJC cope with the distress in their lives through social media. The outcome emphasized the importance of responsible usage of social media.

Accordingly, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought abrupt changes to the population in all ages, and these situations have disturbed their balance, which according to the American Psychological Association (2020), human beings resort to coping mechanisms in order to restore it.

With that, the result is similar to the studies of Xiang et al., (2020) and Moore et al., (2020) when they reported that during the pandemic there had been a great increase in the number of hours spent using the phone and in social media. Singh, Dixit, and Joshi (2020) indicated that the compulsive social media usage during this time of pandemic served as a coping mechanism; however, it could become an addictive behavior in the long run.

Thus, WHO (2020) alarmed and cautioned, particularly the adolescents, on the diverse effects of over exposure to phone and social media on the physical and mental health. Among the indicated effects are problems in sleep, self-esteem, well-being, and functioning, and Gao, Cattelino, Baiocco, Trumello, Babore, Candelori and Chirumbolo (2020) reported that those who were frequently exposed to social media had high odds of anxiety, or a combination of depression and anxiety.

However, Kaya (2020) stated that, in this time of pandemic, people engaged in social media to retrieve information, and to be socially aware and knowledgeable. Additionally, it has also become a tool in the academic and work-related purposes.

Significant Relationship between the Profile and the Health

The study was determined to know whether age, gender, grade level, and total monthly family income profile influenced the effect of

the pandemic on the health.

Age and Health. Table 12 projects the result on the correlation between age profile and health. Eta test statistic correlation was the statistical tool used, where the result must be higher than the tolerance value of 0.200 in order to have a significant relationship.

Table 12. *Coefficient of Correlation between Age Profile and the Health*

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Eta test Statistic	Strength of Relationship	Tolerance Value	Remarks	Decision
Age	Mental	.130	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Physical	.171	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Social	.084	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Spiritual	.235	Weak	0.200	Significant	Reject H01
Overall		.218	Weak	0.200	Significant	Reject H01

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000 Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799 Strong; 0.400 – 0.599 Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399 Weak; 0 – 0.199 Very Weak

Table 12 shows the result on the relationship between age and the four health indicators. Notably, the correlation between age and spiritual health indicators garners an Eta test statistic of .235, and the overall correlation shows a .218 Eta test statistic.

The result reveals that spiritual health showed a weak strength of relationship with age while the mental, physical and social health revealed a very weak strength of relationship. Furthermore, the Eta test statistic value was above the tolerance value of .200, indicating that the association was statistically significant. Furthermore, the three health indicators, namely mental, physical, and social health, were discovered to have no significant link with age. But, when the four variables were combined to represent the overall health, the result showed an association between age and health. This led to the decision to reject the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

The result signifies that the ages of the respondents influenced the extent of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on their health. The result highlighted that the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the spiritual health, on the other hand, varies with age. Furthermore, the total finding emphasized the implication of spiritual health to the entire health of the person.

One of the factors the researcher considered as the basis of the result was the notion that as the person advanced in age, this resulted in a continuing decline in physical and mental capacity, an increased risk of diseases and eventually death. These changes were tangentially related to a person's chronological age.

The preceding observation suggested that age had a significant impact on the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on health. That as people get older, their ability to prioritize their health improved; however, at a biological level, ageing eventually affected and damaged the health over time.

According to Atchley (2017), a person's ability to transcend attitudes toward self, others, and worldly experience is dependent on their wisdom. However, the knowledge either deepens or deteriorates with age.

Moreover, if one aspect of the health is disturbed, it stirs an effect on the spiritual health as well. This made spiritual health an important part of health, and Ghaderi et al. (2018) indicated that this aspect of health balanced the various facets of human life, such as the physical, social and mental aspects.

Gender and Health. Table 13 below shows the result on the relationship between gender and health. The Point Biserial correlation was the statistical tool used since gender has only two variables. To determine the significance of the relationship, the 0.05 level of significance was used as a reference.

Table 13. *Coefficient of Correlation between Gender Profile and the Health*

Profile	Health Indicators	Point Biserial Correlation <i>r_{pb}</i>	Strength of Relationship	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Gender	Mental	.234	Weak	.000	Significant	Reject H01
	Physical	.194	Very Weak	.001	Significant	Reject H01
	Social	-.139	Very Weak Negative	.016	Significant	Reject H01
	Spiritual	.127	Very Weak	.027	Significant	Reject H01
Overall		.203	Weak	.000	Significant	Reject H01

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

Table 13 discloses the result of the correlation between gender and health. It is evident that the table discloses a p-value of .000 for mental health, and the social health reveals a very weak negative strength of the relationship with a point biserial correlation of -.139. The overall correlation between gender and health shows a .203 Point Biserial Correlation, with a .000 p-value.

The data in the table present that mental health significantly got the lowest p- value among the health indicators in the association with gender. This suggested that gender played a crucial influence in the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health. The result reveals that females were greatly affected than the males with an average weighted mean score of 1.62 and 1.35 respectively.

Moreover, only social health showed a very weak negative strength of relationship, which indicated that if one variable increases the

other one decreases. The gathered data were interpreted and analyzed, using numbers to represent the gender. Male was represented by the number one while the female was represented by number two. With that, the very weak negative strength of relationship result indicates that the lesser the number, the greater the extent of the effect. This lesser number, which pertained to number one, refers to male. With that, the association between gender and social health revealed that males were greatly affected than females with an average weighted mean score of 2.29 and 2.12 respectively.

Moreover, the Point Biserial correlation result between gender and health reveals that the strength of the relationship was weak, but the low p-value of .000, lower than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the weak strength of the relationship between gender and health was statistically significant. The overall result on the correlation between gender and health indicated a significant relationship. This suggested that there was a significant relationship between gender and the health, thus leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This revealed that the degree of the impact of the pandemic on their health varied between males and females. The females were more affected in their mental, physical, and spiritual health, whereas males were much affected in terms of their social health.

These varied extent of the effect of the pandemic on health was attributed to the different hormonal make-up between male and female. The varied hormonal components revealed that the female was characterized as a worrier compared to the male, and the current situation has triggered and heightened some concerns that lead them to worry more and be stressed out. Also, females were known to be expressive, and more inclined to connect to friends through social media, and vent all their cares and troubles while males, on the other hand, were more inclined to keep their emotions. This made male respondents more vulnerable in terms of their social health.

Given the above observation, the result implies that the extent of the COVID- 19 pandemic on the four health indicators varies between males and females, which inferred that gender was a predictor of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health, and it certainly played a vital role in the health determinants and consequences. Moreover, there was a need to take into consideration these gender differences to better understand the health experiences and to find intervention to prevent greater impact in the long term.

The result is similar to the studies of Spagnolo, Manson and Joffe (2020) and Matud (2017) which stated that gender was among the most important factors in reference to the impact on health and disease outcomes especially this time of COVID-19 pandemic. Also, Berenbaum and Beltz (2016) declared that many fundamental psychological qualities revealed sex variations and were regulated by sex hormones at distinct developmental phases.

The varied descriptions on the extent of the effects of the pandemic on the four health indicators from slightly affected physical and mental health, affected social health, and to the very much affected spiritual health, suggest that the COVID-19 pandemic had caused a disturbance on the health; however, it is disclosed that the level of impact on each health indicator diverged. The effects of the pandemic on the respondents were varied.

The finding implies that the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the health of the SHS students. Furthermore, the current situation has caused varying degrees of disruption to the four health indicators, with spiritual health profoundly affected. Spiritual health was a vulnerable aspect among the health considered in the study.

The result of the present study is similar to numerous research on the disruptive effect of the pandemic that has currently posed a threat to the health of the population of all ages (WHO, 2020) and has taken millions of lives. Terada (2020) emphasized that the pandemic situation likely worsened an existing health problem or led to an additional health problem (Torales et al., 2020; Kontoangelos et al., 2020) since the pandemic has abruptly changed the lifestyle (Zheng et al., 2020) and the adherence to these changes have been stressful to everyone, which leads to a negative consequence to health even to children and adolescents (Joseph et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the result of the current study has pointed to the significant impact of the pandemic on spiritual health. Spiritual health is an integral part of health, and Ghaderi et al. (2018) indicate that this aspect balances the various facets of human life, such as the physical, social and mental aspects. Thus, if one aspect of the health was disturbed, it stirs an effect on the spiritual health as well. This notion about spiritual health draws much consideration in health-related research (Jaberi et al., 2019).

Grade Level Profile and the Health. The Senior High School program consisted of two grade levels, Grade 11, and Grade 12. To identify the relationship between grade level and health, the Point Biserial correlation was used, with the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 14 displays the findings of the association between grade level and health. The table reveals that the association between grade level and all four health indicators got a negative point biserial correlation particularly mental health with a -.006 result, physical health with a -.077, social health with -.070 and spiritual health with -.021. In general, the association between grade level and the health garnered a p-value .915.

The result shows that all four health indicators garnered a negative point biserial result, which led to a very weak negative strength of relationship. However, their p-value was remarkably higher than the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that the association between grade level and mental, physical, social and spiritual health was not statistically found significant.

Likewise, the .763 p-value result of the overall correlation between grade level and health shows higher than the 0.05 level of significance. This reveals that the association between grade level and health was not significant. This led to the rejection of the null

hypothesis.

Table 14. *Coefficient of Correlation between Grade Level and Health*

Profile	Health Indicators	Point Biserial Correlation rpb	Strength of Relationship	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Grade Level	Mental	-.006	Very Weak Negative	.915	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Physical	-.077	Very Weak Negative	.183	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Social	-.070	Very Weak Negative	.227	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Spiritual	-.021	Very Weak Negative	.713	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
Overall		-.017	Very Weak Negative	.763	Not Significant	Not to reject H01

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

It was noticeable that the correlation between grade level and the four health indicators both got a very weak negative strength of the relationship. Specifically, the health of the Grade 12 learners got an average weighted mean scores for mental, physical, social and spiritual 1.485, 1.155, 2.25 and 2.25 respectively, showing that it was much more affected than the Grade 11, with a result of 1.49 for mental, 1.25 for the physical, 2.165 for the social and 2.165 for the spiritual. However, this result was not statistically found significant.

The result implies that the grade level was not a predictor of the extent of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health. Also, it is inferred that the education level and cognitive maturity of an individual does not guarantee to be not affected by the challenges posed by the pandemic to the health. The significance of the correlation test shows that grade level was independent of one's health.

The result is in contrast to the studies of Desamparado, Mendoza, Minguito and Moneva (2019), and Zhang, Dimitriou and Halstead (2020), who discovered that those students in higher grade levels manifested a greater degree of effect on their health than the lower grades, and emphasized that the extent of the impact of the pandemic depended on the level of education. Among the factors that influenced the result was the varied and tightly packed curriculum in each grade level; the higher grades manifested great fear that the new modality of learning hindered the progress of their studies, their experiences and their maturity level.

Combined Monthly Family Income Profile and the Health. The table projects the result on the correlation between income profile and health. For this study, the income was clustered into poor, low-income, lower-middle, and middle-middle class. Eta correlation was used to indicate a significant relationship; the result must be higher than the tolerance value of 0.200.

The correlation between Combined Monthly Family Income and Health is revealed in Table 16. The figures in the table reveal that the association between the combined monthly family income and the mental, physical, social, spiritual health gets an Eta test result of .104, .181, .087, and .172 correspondingly. The overall correlation gets a 0.107 Eta test value. The result reveals a very weak strength of relationship between health and combined monthly family income. However, the Eta test statistic values were lower than the tolerance value of .200, which indicated that even if combined monthly family income and the four health indicators showed a very weak strength of relationship, it was not found to be statistically significant.

Furthermore, the overall eta test result of 0.107 reveals that it is lower than the tolerance value of 0.200, which means that their relationship is not statistically significant. This led to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the income profile and the extent of the effects of COVID-19 pandemic on the health. The findings imply that the socioeconomic position had little bearing on the severity of the pandemic's impact on their health. That, during this pandemic, people from all areas of life were affected, especially given the worldwide economic recession.

Although most of the studies indicated that socioeconomic served as a factor in the impact of the pandemic on health (Nicola, Alsafi, Sohrabi, Kerwan, Al-Jabir, Iosifidis, Agha & Agha, 2020), the result of the present study was the exact opposite. This was caused by the fact that this was the onset of the implementation of the mitigations and preventive measures, and everyone was still adjusting to it. This signified that the health of the students from poor income class to the middle- middle income class was affected in this time of pandemic.

Table 15. *Coefficient of Correlation between Combined Monthly Family Income and Health*

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Eta test Statistic	Strength of Relationship	Tolerance Value	Remarks	Decision
Combined Family Monthly Income	Mental	.104	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Physical	.181	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Social	.087	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
	Spiritual	.172	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01
Overall		.107	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H01

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

Health and Academic Performance

Health pertains to the mental, physical, social and spiritual health. The Eta test statistic was used to determine how significant the relationship between the health with the academic performance of the students. Table 16 reveals the result.

Table 16 discloses the significant the relationship between health and academic performance. The figures in the table reveal that the correlation between physical health and academic performance gets a 0.402 Eta test statistic result. The Social health gets a 0.346 Eta test statistic. The overall correlation gets a 0.482 result.

The findings highlight that among the health indicators, the physical health got the highest eta test value of 0.402, which indicated that the physical health had a greater vital influence on the academic achievement of the learners than the other health indicators. The social health got the lowest eta test value of 0.346 in the inquiry of identifying their relationship. This result highlights that among the four health indicators, the social health had a little influence on the academic performance of the students, but this slight impact was found significant.

When all health indicators were taken collectively, the overall mean score is 0.482, indicating a moderately strong strength of relationship between health and academic performance. The overall outcome was higher than the tolerance value of 0.200, which suggests that health and academic performance showed a significant relationship. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

As highlighted in the result, health was one of the factors that affected the academic achievement of the students. Particularly striking was the physical health. This suggested that if a student tended to manifest sickness and other health issues, there was difficulty in the participation and involvement with academic related activities, resulting to a low or failing grade.

Conversely, the lower social health result indicated that even if the student was socially affected, still it did not determine a high influence of effect to the academic performance of the students. These learners could make their academic endeavor as their way of coping with any social health concerns.

The finding implies that a person's health aids them in their academic success. That their general health was critical to the success of their academic effort. This encouraged the schools to continuously monitor the students' health in order to have healthier students and a better future for the country.

Table 16. Coefficient of Correlation between Health and Academic Performance

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Eta test Statistic</i>	<i>Strength of Relationship</i>	<i>Tolerance Value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Mental	Academic Performance	0.353	Weak	0.200	Significant	Reject H02
Physical		0.402	Moderately Strong	0.200	Significant	Reject H02
Social		0.346	Weak	0.200	Significant	Reject H02
Spiritual		0.398	Weak	0.200	Significant	Reject H02
Overall		.482	Moderately Strong	0.200	Significant	Reject H02

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

This finding conforms to the established study of Matingwina (2018), who stated that students with better health achieved high academic performance than the students with poor health. Also, CDC (2021) reported that learners who were physically healthy learned better, and this academic success manifested a lifetime influence on health.

Furthermore, El Ansari, Suominen and Draper (2017) indicated that health- conscious and physically active learners academically performed better than those students who were not. Furthermore, most research literature has indicated that those students who were healthy were at a little risk for academic failures compared to learners with poor health. The effects of poor health could lead to poor retention, school failure, grade retention, dropout, absenteeism, and poor concentration.

Profile and the Coping Mechanisms

The present study aimed to determine if there was a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of the employment of coping mechanisms. To determine the relationships between these variables, the Eta test statistic and Point Biserial Correlation was used.

Age and Coping Mechanisms. Table 17 below shows the result on the correlation between age and coping mechanisms. The Eta test correlation was used to determine the association between the two variables.

Table 17. Cross Analysis of Age Profile and Coping Mechanisms

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Eta test Statistic</i>	<i>Strength of Relationship</i>	<i>Tolerance Value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age	Coping Mechanisms	.036	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H03

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

Table 17 reveals the correlation between age and coping mechanism with a 0.36 Eta test statistic result. The Eta test result was significantly lower than the 0.200 tolerance value. This proved that the correlation between age and coping mechanisms was not statistically found significant, which led to the non-rejection of the null hypothesis.

The result implies that age does not influence the degree of employment of coping mechanisms. This strongly illustrates that people of all ages have the tendency to deal with the challenges and struggles brought by the pandemic through coping mechanisms. The choices of coping mechanisms employed might differ but the extent of employment does not.

However, the responders' ages did not differ much in the gaps. All of them belonged to the adolescent stage which signified that their developmental needs and likes were quite of the same preferences. In relation to the preferred coping mechanisms that the respondents indicated, majority of them stated that they were inclined to use their mobile phones and social media at a maximum time of the day. With that, this limitation has affected the result of no significant relationship between age and coping mechanisms.

The outcome of the study is in contrast to the findings of the study of Chen, Peng, Xu and O'Brien (2017) who presented a different result. They discovered that younger and older individuals varied in their coping mechanisms, and Lee et al. (2017) and Man et al. (2020) emphasized that older adults differ in the type of coping mechanisms than the younger adults.

However, the result of the present study was in contradiction to the above-mentioned research. One of the factors that the researcher considered was that the ages of the 300 respondents were closer in range and are collectively known to be at the same developmental stage.

In addition, according to Chowdhury (2020), all human beings have an insight on how to deal with stressful situations in order to regain the balance in life, and people in all ages have a built-in trouble shoot program to counter-act stressful situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Gender and Coping Mechanisms. The table below displays the result on the correlation between Gender and Coping mechanisms. The Point Biserial Correlation was used in the determination of the association.

Table 18. Cross Analysis of Gender and Coping Mechanisms

Profile	Point Biserial Correlation rpb	Strength of Relationship	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Gender	-0.172	Very Weak Negative	.003	Significant	Reject H03

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

Table 18 displays the result of the association between gender and coping mechanisms. The table reveals a - 0.172 Point Biserial correlation, which points to a very weak negative strength of relationship, and a p-value of 0.003.

The result indicates that the association between gender and coping mechanisms showed a very weak negative strength of relationship. Specifically, the very weak negative result revealed that the male respondents with an average weighted mean score of 1.65 manifested a greater extent of coping employment than female respondents with an average weighted mean score of 1.54.

The p-value result was lower than the 0.05 level of significance which indicates that the association between the two variables was statistically significant. This led to the decision to reject the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

The result suggests that gender influenced the extent of the employment of coping mechanisms. Being a male or a female has a significant influence on the employment of coping mechanisms. This result highlights that male and female varies in their level and manners of coping.

The result is similar to the studies of Janney (2018) and Ling, Xianxiu and Xiaowei (2020), which have proven the significant role of gender in the coping mechanisms. Accordingly, gender was considered a factor that affected the identification of whether the situation was stressful or not, as well as the coping responses and health implications of the stress process.

Grade Level Profile and Coping Mechanisms. The table below displays the result on the correlation between grade level and coping mechanisms. The Point Biserial Correlation was used in the determination of the association, with the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 19 shows the outcome of the relationship between Grade Level and Coping Mechanisms. The figures in the table show that grade level and coping mechanisms has a very weak strength of relationship with a .072 Point Biserial Correlation. The p-value of 0.211 is higher than the 0.05 level of significance indicating that there was no significant relationship between grade level and coping mechanisms. This led to the decision to accept the null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between Grade Level and Coping Mechanisms.

Table 19. Cross Analysis of Grade Level and Coping Mechanisms

Profile	Point Biserial Correlation rpb	Strength of Relationship	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Grade Level	.072	Very Weak	.211	Not Significant	Not to Reject H03

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

The grade level has no bearing on the students' use of coping techniques. This indicates that coping employment was not determined by educational attainment or level of schooling. It was noted that each grade level provided a different amount of difficulty and competences to comply with. These difficulties, however, have little relevance on the extent to which the person employs coping strategies.

The result indicates that the grade level is not a determinant to the extent of the employment of coping mechanisms. Although Brilantes et al. (2019) indicate that each grade level presents different degrees of learning tasks and responsibilities, the result of the present study shows the opposite.

Freire, Ferradas, Regueiro, Rodriguez, Valle, and Nuñez (2020), in their study, uncovered a similar result, that year level had no statistically significant influence on the employment of coping mechanisms. Moreover, learners in 11th and 12th grades have learned to employ different ways of coping strategies as they go through the pandemic (Bangayan, Ambagan, Rosales & Maming, 2021).

Combined Family Monthly Income and Coping Mechanisms. Table 21 displays the correlation between combined family monthly income and coping mechanisms. To determine the strength of association, the Eta correlation was used, and in order to have a significant relationship, the Eta correlation result must be higher than the tolerance value of 0.200.

Table 20 indicates that the Eta test statistic is .075 that points to a very weak strength of relationship. Correspondingly, the result implies that the combined monthly family income and coping mechanisms have a very weak association altogether and the lower Eta test statistic result proved that the relationship was not statistically significant. This led to the decision of not rejecting the null hypothesis.

In terms of income cluster, most of the respondents belonged to the poor income group. This indicates that because the income data were not varied, this has influenced the result of no significant relationship. The present study contrasted with most reviewed literature that emphasized on the crucial role the socioeconomics played in the level of coping mechanisms employed.

Table 20. *Cross Analysis of Combined Family Monthly Income and Coping Mechanisms*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Eta test Statistic</i>	<i>Strength of Relationship</i>	<i>Tolerance Value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Combine Family Monthly Income	Coping Mechanisms	.075	Very Weak	0.200	Not Significant	Not to reject H03

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

The finding implies that the respondents' total monthly family income had no effect on the use of coping methods. It also signifies that both poor and middle- middle-class respondents used coping mechanisms to the same extent, demonstrating that money and resources have no influence on the level of coping mechanisms and that, coping was used by all people in all walks of life to deal with adversity.

The study of Atal and Cheng (2016) explains that although socioeconomic status may not have a significant relationship with coping mechanisms, however, individual differences in coping and being flexible may be influenced by the socioeconomic environment of an individual. In addition, although the combined family monthly income has no significant relationship with coping, nevertheless, the availability of resources was considered to influence the kind of coping mechanisms employed by the respondents.

Coping Mechanisms and Academic Performance

The strength of association between coping mechanisms and academic performance was determined using the Eta Test Coefficient. The table below reveals the result.

Table 21. *Cross Analysis between Coping Mechanisms and Academic Performance*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Eta Test Statistic</i>	<i>Strength of Relationship</i>	<i>Tolerance Value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Coping Mechanisms	Academic Performance	.281	Weak	0.200	Significant	Reject H04

Legend: 0.800 – 1.000, Very Strong; 0.600 – 0.799, Strong; 0.400 – 0.599, Moderately Strong; 0.200 – 0.399, Weak; 0 – 0.199, Very Weak

Table 21 projects the Eta Test Statistic result of the strength of association between coping mechanisms and academic performance. The table shows a 0.281 Eta test statistic result, which falls into a weak strength of relationship description.

The result indicates that the Eta test statistic result was significantly higher than the minimum tolerance value of 0.200, which means that the association between coping mechanisms and academic performance was significant. This signifies that even if the strength of relationship was weak still the association was statistically significant. Thus, leading to the decision to reject the null hypothesis.

In this study, majority of the students had indicated that they often employed coping strategies which helped them deal with their academic challenges in this time of pandemic. This resulted to a better academic performance. The result implies that the level of coping mechanisms employed had a significant impact on the academic performance of the students.

Researches declare that those who employed coping performs better in school, and were academically involved (Yazon, Ang-Manaig & Tesoro, 2016; Nwosu, Okwuduba & Okoye, 2018). In addition, the study of Osorio and Sanchez (2021) pointed out that the academic endeavor of a student served as a strategy to cope up with difficult situations in life.

Significant Difference in the Coping Mechanisms when grouped together according to their profile

The aim of this inquiry was to identify if there was a significant difference in the employment of coping when grouped according to their profile. The profile included the age, gender, grade level, and combined family monthly income. The tables below show the results.

Coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their Age. To determine the significant difference in coping mechanisms

when grouped together according to their age profile, the Analysis of Variance was used at a 0.05 level of significance. The outcome is projected in the table below.

Table 22. *Significant Difference in Coping Mechanisms when Grouped according to their Age*

Age	df	F	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Between Groups	3			No Significant Difference	Not to reject H05
Within Groups	296	.126	.945		
Total	299				

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 22 displays the result of the analysis on the significant difference in coping when grouped together according to their age. The figures in the table shows a p-value of 0.945, which is significantly higher than the 0.05 level of significance.

The result indicates that there was no significant difference in coping mechanisms when the respondents were grouped together according to their age. The result led to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis. The finding signifies the notion that there was no measurable difference between age and coping mechanisms.

Another aspect that the researcher considers was the fact that most of the respondents were of the same developmental age. Their preferences, developmental needs, and the manners of coping with the challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic were the same. Human beings of all ages, according to Ackerman, Tybur and Blackwell (2021), encounter tough and trying circumstances, and an individual has his own and effective behaviors to cope with and bounce forward from these conditions, which make coping mechanisms a significant part of a human behavior.

Withal, the researcher put into consideration the fact that the ages of the respondents in this study were not diverse. However, most of the research indicate that older respondents and adolescents differ in coping strategies (Man et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2016).

Coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their Gender. The Analysis of Variance was used at a 0.05 level of significance to identify the significant difference in coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their gender profile. The table below discloses the result.

Table 23. *Significant Difference in Coping Mechanisms when Grouped according to Gender*

Gender	Mean	Mean Difference	t-test	df	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Male	1.653						
		0.115	3.008	298	.003	Significant Difference	Reject H05
Female	1.537						

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 23 reveals the result on how significant the difference in coping mechanisms when the respondents were grouped together according to their gender. The extent of the coping mechanisms among the male respondents gained a mean score of 1.653, while a mean score of 1.537 for the female, with a 0.115 mean difference. The p-value of 0.003 was lower than the 0.05 level of significance. The result indicates that the significantly higher mean score for males manifested a higher extent of coping mechanisms than the females. It is revealed that the males had employed the coping often while females only did it sometimes. The consolidated coping mechanisms result reveal a varied extent of coping mechanisms employment between males and females.

Moreover, the significantly lower p-value of 0.003 indicates that there was a significant difference in coping mechanisms when they were grouped together according to their gender, which led to the decision to reject the null hypothesis. Gender has a significant effect on one's coping mechanism.

The result implies that gender influences the extent of employment of coping mechanisms. It was noted that males and females differed in the activities they preferred as a way of coping through this pandemic period. Likewise, the male respondents showed a significantly higher level of coping than females. The result of the study is similar to the findings of Liddon, Kinglerlee and Barry (2017), and Graves, Hall, Dias-Karch, Haischer and Apter (2021), which emphasized that males and females varied in the extent of coping employment, the manner of coping and the preferences in coping, due to their different hormonal make-up (Bonneville-Roussya, Evans, Filion, Valler & Bouffard, 2016; Rodriguez- Hidalgo et al., 2020).

Coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their Grade Level. The Analysis of Variance was used at a 0.05 level of significance to determine the significant difference in coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their grade level profile. The table below displays the result.

Table 24. *Significant Difference in Coping Mechanisms when Grouped according to Grade Level*

Profile	Mean	Mean Difference	t-test	df	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Grade Level							
Grade 11	1.57						
Grade 12	1.62	0.05	1.254	298	0.211	No Significant Difference	Not to reject H05

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 24 reveals the result of how significant the difference in coping mechanisms when respondents were grouped together according to their grade level. It discloses that Grade 12 shows a higher mean score of 1.62 in coping mechanisms than the Grade 11 with a 1.57 mean score result, which results to a 0.05 mean difference. Also, it reveals a low t-test score of 1.25 and a p-value of 0.211.

The result indicates that there was a difference on the extent of the employment of mechanisms between Grade 11 and Grade 12, favoring the latter. However, the t-test result of 1.25 signifies that the groups had shown similarity on the extent of the employment of the coping mechanisms, that the 0.05 mean difference was a minimal value to determine a significant difference. Regardless of the year level of the respondents, they employed coping mechanisms in order to adjust with an existing crisis.

The findings suggest that with the COVID-19 pandemic, both respondents from Grade 11 and 12, dealt with the COVID-19 pandemic through coping mechanisms at the same degree. Also, it pointed out that the varied competencies experienced in each grade level did not influence the extent of the employment. Furthermore, the 0.211 p-value result was evidently higher than the 0.05 level of significance, which indicates that there was no significant difference in coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their profile.

With the foregoing analysis, discussion, and interpretation of the results, it is implied that both respondents from each grade level employed coping mechanisms at the same degree and that the cognitive development, different competencies and performance tasks from each grade level did not influence the intensity of the employment of coping. Higher educational attainment is not a guarantee of a better coping mechanism. According to Bangayan et al. (2021), the Grade 11 and 12 learners employed different ways and strategies of coping as they went through the pandemic, and Freire et al. (2020) indicated that the grade level did not influence the degree of employment of coping.

Coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their Combined Family Monthly Income. To determine the significant difference in coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their Combined Family Monthly Income profile, the Analysis of Variance was used at a 0.05 level of significance. The table below displays the result.

The table reveals the result on the significant difference in the extent of the employment of coping mechanisms when grouped according to their combined monthly family income. That data show that the p-value results to 0.636.

The p-value is evidently higher than the $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. This suggests that there was no significant difference in the coping mechanisms of the respondents when they were grouped according to their income clusters, that the respondents who belonged to poor (55.33%), low-income (24%), lower-middle (9%) and middle-middle income clusters 11.67% (see Table 5) all employed coping mechanisms at the same degree. The resources and the financial concerns that go with each income clusters do not influence the degree of employment to coping mechanisms. The economic status of the family could not be used as a predictor on how the individual employed his/her coping mechanism.

Table 25. Significant Difference in Coping Mechanisms when Grouped according to Combined Family Monthly Income

Combined Family Monthly Income	df	F	p-Value	Remarks	Decision
Between Groups	3			No Significant Difference	
Within Groups	296	.565	.636		Not to reject H05
Total	299				

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

With the above result, it led to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis of no significant difference in coping mechanisms when grouped together according to their combined family monthly income profile. The findings of the study imply that the respondents from the different income clusters practiced coping mechanisms at the same degree. The different economic status, the resources that go with it, the privileges or deprivations experienced due to finances, do not influence the degree of their employment. Each person has his/her unique way of coping that was independent of the economic status of the family.

PSA (2021) reported that in this time of pandemic, economic loss and recession were evident especially when some jobs were put off and the closures of business were mandated. This made all citizens from different walks of life experienced difficulties which prompted them to find different manners of dealing with it. The economic status has the tendency to affect the availability of resources and types of coping mechanisms applied in their lives; however, it does not affect the extent of employment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are given.

Most of the students were within the age qualification for SHS in the Philippine Educational System. They all belonged to the developmental period known as the adolescence stage. There is a balance representation of gender and grade level of the respondents. A variety of income clusters are manifested. However, most of the SHS students studying at Saint Joseph College were within the poor income clusters.

The mental, physical, social, and spiritual indicators of health were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic in varying degrees.

The results revealed that some students performed well in their academics despite the new learning modalities for which they must adapt and adjust.

Using social media at a maximum time of the day helped students deal with difficult situations; this coping mechanism might be detrimental to one's health in the long run. Healthy coping mechanisms must be taught to students.

One of the significant predictors of health is gender. Females are more prone to the ill-effects of the pandemic to their physical and mental health than males. However, males are more affected in social and spiritual health than females.

In the study, it is further confirmed that health is a determinant factor of academic performance.

Gender influences the employment of coping mechanisms. Males are better than females in the employment of coping mechanisms.

The employment of coping mechanisms could affect academic performance. The better the employment coping mechanisms, the better the performance.

Coping mechanisms vary, and gender could alter how one would employ his/her chosen to cope.

Given the information with regards to the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health, academic performance, and coping mechanisms of the students, and after thorough analysis, interpretation, implication, and conclusion, the following recommendations are stated:

Constant monitoring and follow-up of the status of students shall be done through constant communication with them or through their parents and guardians. Interactive activities that shall be initiated by the Guidance Office and with the

Homeroom advisers must be done monthly or as frequently as possible to give students a venue to air issues and concerns pertinent to school works and non- academics.

The teachers should be given the information of the status of their respective students in this time of crisis so they may be able to plan accordingly. They may also be given the necessary assistance through a seminar workshop to handle students with issues and concerns regarding the effects of the new normal.

The parents may be oriented and trained on how to monitor closely their children's overall health, especially the mental, physical and social health, which is the most compromised in these times of the pandemic.

School Guidance Counselors and Advocates must continually conduct Health awareness programs, counseling, and group dynamics designed to address the issues and health problems. Also, to revisit their Guidance Program to assess if the needs of the students were still catered by the existing programs.

School Administrators such as the Campus Ministry Directors and Coordinators must revisit existing practices and innovate programs to help develop spiritual maturity and avail new modalities to cater to the spiritual needs and development of the students.

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